

200 Epochs

400 Epochs:

These are the values obtained after feature removal for the first model:

Iterations	Loss (prediction)	Accuracy (prediction)
10	0.847	0.957
15	0.438	0.975
20	0.176	0.985
25	0.105	0.992

30	0.063	0.992
35	0.036	0.992
40	0.030	0.992

Ablation Study:

We've made a few changes to zoom features data, based upon the number of features in each release.

- In the first 'CH_01_Zoom-features-2025' file, we have removed feature with less features release
- To be specific, we've removed the released feature 'webinar features' from all the months jan, feb, march. Below are the results we've observed

	Epochs	Train Loss	Val Loss	Train Acc	Val Acc
0	10	0.808714	1.152169	0.957143	0.814
1	15	0.384176	0.902552	0.978571	0.804
2	20	0.227831	0.743386	0.985714	0.822
3	25	0.124283	0.799236	0.992857	0.774
4	30	0.057370	0.642176	1.000000	0.810
5	35	0.042821	0.716762	1.000000	0.764
6	40	0.029776	0.663162	1.000000	0.800
7	45	0.021383	0.694812	1.000000	0.790
8	50	0.017940	0.633782	1.000000	0.806

Most frequent features removal: team chat feature:

	Epochs	Train Loss	Val Loss	Train Acc	Val Acc
0	10	0.651473	1.155549	0.978571	0.766
1	15	0.338258	0.949942	0.985714	0.770
2	20	0.200112	0.842222	0.992857	0.758
3	25	0.092157	0.716770	0.992857	0.802
4	30	0.076396	0.702187	1.000000	0.798
5	35	0.043709	0.842763	1.000000	0.756
6	40	0.025243	0.688738	1.000000	0.790
7	45	0.023391	0.692550	1.000000	0.782
8	50	0.015914	0.680677	1.000000	0.792

Loss vs Epochs (10 → 50)

